

IR4422-98-3-6-1, a promising variety for irrigated systems in Bihar, India

S. Saran, R. C. Chaudhary, Kr. J. P. Sinha, H. K. Suri, and S. K. Choudhary, Rajendra Agricultural University, Bihar, Agricultural Research Institute, Mithapur, Patna, India

IR4422-98-3-6-1, from the cross IR2049-134-2/IR2061-125-37, developed at IRRI, was first tested in Bihar in 1977 (IRYN-M) against checks IR8 and IR26. IR4422-98-3-6-1 yielded 5 t/ha against 3.6 t/ha for IR8 and 4.6 t/ha for IR26.

IR4422-98-3-6-1 was shifted to Uniform Variety Trial 3 for multilocational testing against local check varieties Sita and Jaya during the 1978, 1979, and 1980 wet seasons. It gave consistently better yields than the check varieties at almost all sites (see table) and is now being tested in the minikit test program

Performance of IR4422-98-3-6-3 in Uniform Variety Trial 3 at Bihar, India.

Year and variety	Yield ^a (t/ha)			Mean	Yield increase (%) over check
	Patna	Bikramganj	Pusa		
<i>1978</i>					
IR4422-98-3-6-1	6.3	5.4	4.8	5.5	
Sita	5.1	4.3	3.6	4.3	26.7
Jaya	4.5	—	3.8	4.2	31.0
CD at 5%	839	1206	739		
CV	9.36	11.8	12.31		
<i>1979</i>					
IR4422-98-3-6-3	4.4	7.6	2.9	5.0	
Sita	3.6	7.9	3.1	4.8	2.2
Jaya	3.7	7.2	3.2	4.7	5.9
CD at 5%	147	1055	632		
CV	10.44	9.69	12.45		
<i>1980</i>					
IR4422-98-3-6-1	3.6	6.8	4.7	5.0	
Sita	3.2	5.4	3.9	4.2	20.4
Jaya	2.4	6.4	4.6	4.4	13.4
CD at 5%	1064	906	300		
CV	14.14	9.27	14.4		

^a**Means significant difference

in farmers' fields.

Semidwarf IR4422-98-3-6-1 takes 135-140 days from seeding to ripening in

Bihar and fits local multicropped irrigated systems well. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Agronomic characteristics

Screening rice varieties for photoperiod sensitivity

S. Ghosh and S. Saran, Rajendra Agricultural University, Bihar, Agricultural Research Institute, Mithapur, Patna, India

Photoperiod sensitivity is an important consideration for rainfed wetland rices. To identify photoperiod sensitivity, 30

popular and promising rice varieties were sown from 16 May to 16 September at 2-week intervals. Varieties in which days to flowering differed by 5-15 days were classified photoperiod insensitive. Varieties with differences of 16-50 days were classified weakly photoperiod sensitive and those with differences of 51-70 days were classified photoperiod

sensitive (Table 1).

Degree of photoperiod sensitivity also was calculated by

$$\frac{X - Y \times 100}{X}$$

where X = flowering duration due to long day effect (16 May sowing) and Y = flowering duration to short day effect (16 August sowing). Photoperiod sensitivities of 15 varieties are shown in Table 2. ■

Table 1. Varietal photoperiod sensitivity at Mithapur, Patna, India.

Insensitive	Weakly sensitive	Sensitive
IET2815	BIET452	BIET613
IET2895	BIET460	BIET653
IET3257	BIET599	BIET820
IET5656	BIET720	BIET821
		C64-117
Rajendra	BIET724	Barobar
Dhan 201		
BG90-2		Janeria
BIET1084		Kabra
BIET1107		Jalaj
Sita (C)		Bajra
Pankaj (C)		Bhutahi
		Bajal
		Cuttack Basmati
		BR34 (check)
		BR8 (check)

Table 2. Degree of varietal photoperiod sensitivity at Mithapur, Patna, India.

Variety	Flowering duration (days)		Difference (days) (X - Y)	Degree of sensitivity $X - Y \times 100 / X$
	Preceded by long day (X)	Preceded by short day (Y)		
BIET613	154	89	65	42.2
BIET653	153	90	63	41.1
BIET820	165	86	79	47.9
BIET821	164	87	77	47.0
C64-117	158	89	69	43.7
Barobar	159	89	70	44.0
Janeria	164	90	74	45.1
Kabra	166	89	77	46.4
Jalaj	160	89	71	44.9
Bajra	161	88	73	45.3
Bhutahi	159	92	67	42.1
Bajal	161	89	72	44.1
Cuttack Basmati	161	91	70	43.5
BR34	153	87	66	43.1
BR8	159	89	70	44.0